

NDAC/LO/126
Aug 31, 1989

29th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

The preparation and sorting modules have been modified according to the most recent interface specifications (GCOS-2). A tape with 23 test sets from RGO/CUO has been received but not yet analysed. Additional work has been made on graphical routines for ANAL23 and general purposes.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

Further tests of the new STDDBLs program have been made with simulations covering one year of observations. (C , C). As expected, some 25% of the solutions with poor a priori data are incorrect ('grid-step error'). The problem is worse at low ecliptic latitude and with large magnitude differences, but it is possible to find areas in the lat/ Δm -plane where *all* solutions are correct.

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

A simulation of sky coverage and astrometric accuracy for a 'recovery mission' in a raised transfer orbit was started during the last week of August. Results should be available by September 8.

Working papers:

- C =NDAC/LO/124 (Söderhjelm, 1989 July 6):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Xb
- C =NDAC/LO/125 (Söderhjelm, 1989 Aug 22):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Xc